

SUDBINA, REKUPERACIJA I PONOVNNA UPOTREBA CELULOZE SA POSTROJENJA ZA PREČIŠĆAVANJE OTPADNIH VODA

FATE, RECOVERY AND VALORIZATION OF CELLULOSE FROM WASTEWATER TREATMENT PLANTS

IZVOD

Postrojenja za tretman otpadnih voda polako se transformišu u postrojenja za rekuperaciju resursa iz otpadnih voda. Do sada je identifikovan širok spektar proizvoda (sama voda, energija, nutrijenti, itd.) u otpadnim vodama kao i tehnologije rekuperacije. Međutim, samo nekoliko tehnologija je ekstrapolirano u praksu punog obima. Celuloza je takva vrsta resursa koja potiče iz toalet papira i njeno izdvajanje je sprovedeno i podržano istraživačkim naporima u smislu ekološke i ekonomske povoljnosti. Ovaj pregledni rad ima za cilj da sveobuhvatno mapira tehnologije rekuperacije celuloze iz otpadnih voda i da razjasni povezani unutrašnji uticaj i spoljni tržišni potencijal. Prvo, izvor, sudbina i transformacija celuloze u tipičnom postrojenju za tretman otpadnih voda (primenom aktivnog mulja) analiziraju se kako bi se pružio celovit pregled potencijala rekuperacije. Drugo, tehnologije rekuperacije celuloze pregledane su i sumirane hronološki sa naglaskom na rotacione filter prese. Posebno, uticaji rekuperacije celuloze na performanse tretmana otpadnih voda i rute valorizacije su sveobuhvatno razmatrani u trećem delu rada kako bi se koristi učinile jasnijim. Imajući u vidu sve pomenuto, rekuperacija celuloze se sa sigurnošću preporučuje u smislu uključivanja u koncept upravljanja otpadnim vodama.

Ključne reči: celuloza, cirkularna ekonomija, rekuperacija, ponovna upotreba, otpadna voda

ABSTRACT

Wastewater treatment plants are evolving into water resource recovery facilities, aiming to maximize resource recovery rather than simply disposing of them. A diverse range of products and recovery technologies have been identified within wastewater, including water, energy nutrients etc.. However, only a handful of these technologies have been implemented on a large scale. Cellulose, derived mainly from toilet paper, is one such resource whose recovery has been researched extensively due to its environmental and economic benefits. This review seeks to comprehensively outline the technologies for cellulose recovery from wastewater, detailing both their internal impact and external market potential. It begins by examining the source, fate, and transformation of cellulose within a typical wastewater treatment plant (using activated sludge) to provide a comprehensive overview of recovery possibilities. Subsequently, cellulose recovery technologies are reviewed and placed in a historical context, with a focus on rotating belt filters. The review also delves into the impacts of cellulose recovery on wastewater treatment performance and valorization routes to elucidate its benefits further. Given its mature value chain, adaptable application routes, and positive environmental impact, integrating cellulose recovery into wastewater management is strongly recommended.

Keywords: cellulose, circular economy, recuperation, product valorization, wastewater

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1. UVOD

Celuloza je među najrasprostranjenijim i najobilnijim prirodnim polisaharidima, igrajući vitalnu ulogu u strukturi biljaka. Celuloza se nalazi i u otpadnim vodama, a potiče mahom iz upotrebe toalet papira koji završava u kanalizacionom sistemu. Otpadne vode pored celuloze mogu sadržati i fizičke, organske ili neorganske hemikalije, biološke ili druge nečistoće. Potrošnja toalet papira po osobi može se posmatrati s obzirom na regionalnu varijaciju. Okvirna srednja potrošnja toalet papira po osobi iznosi 13 kg u toku godinu dana, što predstavlja značajan resurs. Količina prodaje i upotrebe toalet papira varira između zemalja a većina završava u komunalnim otpadnim vodama. Uklanjanje celuloze je prilično teško i zahteva obimne fizičko-hemijske i biološke tretmane, što pak sa druge strane rezultira značajnim kapitalnim i operativnim troškovima postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda. Zagađena voda sadrži proteine, lipide i celulozu, koja je ugljenohidratne prirode, bogata izvorima ugljenika, pa je stoga stopa mikrobiološke razgradnje spora. Biološki potpomognuta hidroliza celuloze veoma je zavisna od temperature i vremena zadržavanja mulja. Različite istraživačke grupe pokušale su da procene i zaključe optimalne uslove, navodeći rezultate koji, nažalost, nisu laki za poređenje (Mushtaq i sar., 2023). Glavni faktori koji se odnose na razgradnju ili eliminaciju celuloze, kao što su potrošnja kiseonika, proizvodnja mulja, sposobnost zgušnjavanja i efikasnost uklanjanja nutrijenata, još uvek nisu temeljno razmotreni. Smatra se da celuloza čini 30% ukupne prisutnosti hemijske potrošnje kiseonika (HPK) u influentima postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda. (Ruiken i sar., 2013). Količina mulja eksponencijalno takođe raste sa svakom prošlom godinom, kako se sve više industrija i stambenih objekata instalira u svetu i priključuje na kanalizacionu mrežu. Trenutno postoje različiti putevi upravljanja i odlaganja otpadnog mulja. Komunalni mulj se smatra potencijalnom biomasom (Abdullah i sar., 2020), rezervom ili resursom, zbog ogromnih količina sastojaka poput proteina, ugljenih hidrata, dodatnih polimernih supstanci, vlaknastih materijala poput celuloze. Ako se ovi sastojci rekuperišu, očekuje se da će smanjiti količinu proizvedenog otpadnog mulja i pružiti, usled hemijske prirode, potencijal za korišćenje rekuperisanih proizvoda u industrijama. Nedavno su Foglia i sar. (2021) sprovedi holističku procenu devet inovativnih tehnologija za rekuperaciju resursa u pogledu investicione isplativosti i društvenih koristi primenjenih u punom obimu komunalnih postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda (PPOV). Resursi/proizvodi na koje su ove tehnologije ciljale uključivali su biogas, različite fosfatne soli (struvit, kalcijum fosfat i đubrivo), biopolimere, kratkolančane masne kiseline (VFAs) i celulozu. Rezultati su pokazali da je rekuperacija celuloze putem mikroprosejavanja

1. INTRODUCTION

Cellulose is among the most widespread and abundant natural polysaccharides, playing a vital role in plant structure. Cellulose is also found in wastewater, primarily originating from the use of toilet paper that ends up in the sewer system. Wastewater can contain physical, organic, or inorganic chemicals, biological, or other impurities. The consumption of toilet paper per person can be observed with respect to regional variation. The average consumption of toilet paper per person is approximately 13 kg per year, representing a significant resource. The amount of toilet paper sales and usage varies between countries, because the majority ends up in municipal wastewater. Cellulose removal is quite difficult and requires extensive physicochemical and biological treatments, which in turn results in significant capital expenditures (CAPEX) and operating expenditures (OPEX) for wastewater treatment plants. Polluted water contains proteins, lipids, and cellulose, which is carbohydrate in nature and rich in carbon sources, thus the rate of microbial degradation is slow. Biologically aided hydrolysis of cellulose is highly dependent on temperature and sludge retention time. Various research groups have attempted to assess and conclude the optimal conditions, citing results that, unfortunately, are not easy to compare (Mushtaq et al., 2023). Principal factors related to the degradation or elimination of cellulose, such as oxygen demand, sludge production, ability to be dewatered, and nutrient removal efficiency, have not been thoroughly considered yet. It is estimated that cellulose constitutes 30% of the total chemical oxygen demand (COD) presence in wastewater influents (Ruiken et al., 2013). The amount of sludge is also growing exponentially each year, as more industries and residential areas are being set up and connected to the sewer network. Currently, there are various routes for waste sludge management and disposal. Municipal sludge is seen as a potential biomass (Abdullah et al., 2020), reserve or resource, due to the huge amounts of constituents such as proteins, carbohydrates, extra polymeric substances, and fibrous materials like cellulose. If these constituents are recovered, it is expected to reduce the amount of waste sludge produced and to provide a potential for using the recovered products in industries due to their chemical nature. Recently, Foglia et al. (2021) conducted a holistic assessment of nine innovative resource recovery technologies in terms of investment sustainability and social benefits applied at the full-scale municipal wastewater treatment plants (WWTP). The resources/products targeted by these technologies including biogas, various phosphate salts (struvite, calcium phosphate, and fertilizer), biopolymers, volatile fatty acids (VFAs), and cellulose. The results showed that cellulose recovery through microsieving achieved the

ostvarila najveće ekonomske i društvene prednosti, uz najmanji uticaj na životnu sredinu. Budući da se jedinica mikroprosejavanja instalira nakon grubih rešetki, rekuperacija celuloze značajno smanjuje organsko opterećenje i potražnju za kiseonikom tokom aeracije, čime se minimizira potrošnja energije, što je opšteprihvaćeno u nekoliko studija (Ruiken i sar., 2013; Ahmed i sar., 2021). Kao uobičajeni industrijski sirov materijal, celuloza se široko koristi u građevinarstvu, prehrambenoj industriji, papirnoj industriji, i tako dalje (Lavanya i sar., 2011). Međutim, rekuperacija celuloze nije dobila očekivanu pažnju i primenu u punom obimu. Takav pristup delimično je posledica nejasnoća u vezi sa negativnim uticajem rekuperacije celuloze na biološko uklanjanje organskog zagađenja, što nije sveobuhvatno obrađeno u prethodnim studijama (Da Ros i sar., 2020; Guest i sar., 2022; Ruiken i sar., 2013). Pored toga, nedostatak sveobuhvatne diskusije o povoljnim uticajima rekuperacije celuloze na PPOV takođe umanjuje preferencu za implementaciju rekuperacije celuloze. Stoga je cilj ovog preglednog rada popuniti ovu prazninu u znanju i sumirati sudbinu i rekuperaciju celuloze u PPOV-ima kako bi se široko promovisala praksa ponovne upotrebe rekuperisane celuloze.

2. IZVORI I MIGRACIJA CELULOZE U POSTROJENJIMA ZA PREČIŠĆAVANJE OTPADNIH VODA.

2.1. Izvori celuloze u otpadnim vodama

Vlakna celuloze koja potiču od korišćenja toalet papira su veoma važan resurs prisutan u postrojenjima za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda, koji poslednjih deset godina dobija još veći značaj. Što se tiče komunalnih otpadnih voda, toalet papir je primarni izvor celuloznih vlakana, a još jedan manji doprinos verovatno potiče od kuhinjskog otpada ili oticanja kišnice (kombinovani kanalizacioni sistem). S obzirom da se celuloza sastoji od teško biorazgradivih organskih materija, logičan je put toalet papira (kao primarnog izvora celuloze na postrojenju za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda) od ulaza u kanalizacionu mrežu, preko raspadanja u cevima (vlakna dužine 1 mm) do konačnog dospevanja na postrojenje za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda u obliku linearnih celuloznih vlakana kao dela suspendovanih materija (SS). Celulozna vlakna mogu predstavljati frakciju do 50% ukupnih SS, te predstavljaju značajan deo suspendovane čvrste frakcije komunalnih otpadnih voda, time i mulja na postrojenju za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda. Od stepena društvenog razvoja i kulturoloških razlika zavisi i specifičnost potrošnje toalet papira odnosno ukupnog sadržaja celuloze u efluentu. Slika 1 sumira potrošnju toaletnog papira i sadržaj celuloze u otpadnim vodama različitih zemalja i regiona. Prosečna potrošnja toaletnog papira po

highest economic and social benefits, with the least environmental impact. Since the microsieving unit is installed after coarse screens, cellulose recovery significantly reduces organic load and oxygen demand during aeration, thereby minimizing energy consumption, which is widely accepted in several studies (Ruiken et al., 2013; Ahmed et al., 2021). As a common industrial raw material, cellulose is widely used in construction, food industry, paper industry, and so on (Lavanya et al., 2011). However, cellulose recovery did not receive the expected attention and full-scale application. This approach is partially due to ambiguities regarding the negative impact of cellulose recovery on biological organic pollution removal, which was not comprehensively addressed in previous studies (Da Ros et al., 2020; Guest et al., 2022; Ruiken et al., 2013). Furthermore, the lack of comprehensive discussion on the favorable impacts of cellulose recovery on WWTPs also reduces the preference for implementing cellulose recovery. Therefore, the aim of this review paper is to fill this knowledge gap and summarize the fate and recovery of cellulose in WWTPs, and to broadly promote the practice of reusing recovered cellulose.

2. SOURCES AND MIGRATION OF CELLULOSE IN WASTEWATER TREATMENT PLANTS

2.1. Sources of Cellulose in Wastewater

Cellulose fibers derived from the use of toilet paper are a highly significant resource presented in wastewater treatment plants, it is gaining even more importance over the past decade. In municipal wastewater, toilet paper is the primary source of cellulose fibers, with a smaller contribution likely coming from kitchen waste or stormwater runoff (in combined sewer systems). Considering that cellulose consists of hard-to-degrade organic matter, the logical pathway of toilet paper (as the primary source of cellulose in wastewater treatment plants) follows its entry into the sewer network, its breakdown in pipes (resulting in fibers approximately 1 mm in length), and its eventual arrival at the wastewater treatment plant as linear cellulose fibers, which are part of the suspended solids (SS). Cellulose fibers can make up to 50% of the total SS, thus representing a significant portion of the suspended solid fraction in municipal wastewater, and consequently, in the sludge at the wastewater treatment plant. The degree of social development and cultural differences also influences the specific consumption of toilet paper and the overall cellulose content in the effluent. Figure 1 summarizes the consumption of toilet paper and the cellulose content in wastewater in various countries and regions. The average consumption of toilet paper per capita is proportional to social development, with specific consumption in North

stanovniku je proporcionalna društvenom razvoju, a specifična potrošnja u Severnoj Americi i zapadnoj Evropi dostiže čak 16 kg/god (Morris, 2019). Na osnovu generisanja otpadne vode, sadržaj celuloze u otpadnim vodama može se izračunati na oko 157~178 mg SS/l, što čini 40~50% ukupnih SS (TSS). Nasuprot tome, sadržaj celuloze u otpadnim vodama je niži u latinoameričkim i afričkim regionima (Armstrong, 2018). Iako je specifična potrošnja toaletnog papira u Kini mnogo niža nego u zapadnoj Evropi, Severnoj Americi ili Japanu (Armstrong, 2018), i nalazi se na istom nivou kao u Latinskoj Americi, niska generacija otpadnih voda po stanovniku čini sadržaj celuloze u otpadnim vodama visokim, otprilike oko 118 mg/l. Računajući na količinu otpadnih voda od 55,465 milijardi tona u 2019. godini (MHURD, 2020), postoji veliki potencijal za praksu rekuparacije celuloze u Kini.

2.2. Sudbina i transformacija celuloze u postrojenjima za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda

Sudbina celuloze u tipičnim gradskim postrojenjima za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda visoko je povezana sa njenim fizičko-hemijskim svojstvima. Celuloza je jedan od najrasprostranjenijih polisaharida na Zemlji i ima važnu ulogu u održavanju strukture biljnih ćelija (Jin i sar., 2021). Celuloza je makromolekul, polisaharid, linearnih lančanih struktura koje čine nekoliko stotina međusobno povezanih jedinica D-glukoze, β -1,4-glukozidnim vezama, sa četiri hidroksilne grupe na jednom kraju i sa tri slobodne hidroksilne grupe i jednom poluacetalnom hidroksilnom grupom na drugom kraju (Chen, 2014). Osnovu celuloze čine u stvari, dva anhidrida D – glukoze, koji su vezani glukozidnom vezom i čine molekul celobioze. Iako polu-acetalna hidroksilna grupa ima slične osobine kao aldehidna grupa, mala količina aldehidnih grupa i dugački lanac smanjuju redukciju celuloze. Pored toga, celuloza se može razgraditi u glukozu pod kiselim i visokotemperaturnim uslovima, jer se hidroliza glikozidnih veza može katalizovati kiselinom. Nasuprot tome, celuloza je stabilnija u alkalnim uslovima, ali u prisustvu kiseonika pri visokim temperaturama, razblaženi rastvor alkalnih soli takođe može smanjiti stepen polimerizacije celuloze (Golova i Nosova, 1973). U lančanoj strukturi celuloze nalazi se mnogo hidroksilnih grupa, što čini celulozu hidrofilnom do određene mere (Chaudemanche i Navard, 2011). Većinom se nalazi u obliku vlakana, koja su vrlo čvrsta, nerastvorna u vodi, slabim kiselinama i bazama, te u organskim rastvaračima. Molekuli celuloze usvajaju produženu i prilično krutu konformaciju nalik štapiću, uz pomoć ekvatorijalne konformacije ostataka glukoze. Višestruke hidroksilne grupe na glukozu iz jednog lanca formiraju vodonične veze sa atomima kiseonika na istom ili na susjednom lancu, držeći lance čvrsto zajedno jedan pored drugog i formirajući mikrofibrole visoke zatezne

America and Western Europe reaching as high as 16 kg/year (Morris, 2019). Based on wastewater generation, the cellulose content in wastewater can be estimated at around 157~178 mg SS/L, accounting for 40~50% of total SS (TSS). Conversely, the cellulose content in wastewater is lower in Latin American and African regions (Armstrong, 2018). Although the specific consumption of toilet paper in China is much lower than in Western Europe, North America, or Japan (Armstrong, 2018), and is at the same level as in Latin America, the low wastewater generation per capita makes the cellulose content in wastewater high, approximately 118 mg/L. Considering the volume of wastewater of 55.465 billion tons in 2019 (MHURD, 2020), there is significant potential for cellulose recovery practices in China.

2.2. The Fate and Transformation of Cellulose in Wastewater Treatment Plants

The fate of cellulose in typical urban wastewater treatment plants is highly correlated with its physical-chemical properties. Cellulose is one of the most widespread polysaccharides on Earth and plays an important role in maintaining the structure of plant cells (Jin et al., 2021). Cellulose is a macromolecule, a polysaccharide, with linear chain structures consisting of several hundred interconnected D-glucose units linked by β -1,4-glucosidic bonds, featuring four hydroxyl groups at one end and three free hydroxyl groups and one hemiacetal hydroxyl group at the other end (Chen, 2014). The fundamental unit of cellulose is two D-glucose anhydrides linked by a glycosidic bond to form a cellobiose molecule. Although the hemiacetal hydroxyl group exhibits characteristics similar to an aldehyde group, the small number of aldehyde groups and the long chain reduce the reduction of cellulose. Moreover, cellulose can be degraded into glucose under acidic and high-temperature conditions, as the hydrolysis of glycosidic bonds can be acid-catalyzed. Conversely, cellulose is more stable under alkaline conditions, but in the presence of oxygen at high temperatures, a dilute solution of alkaline salts can also reduce the degree of polymerization of cellulose (Golova and Nosova, 1973). The chain structure of cellulose contains many hydroxyl groups, making cellulose somewhat hydrophilic (Chaudemanche and Navard, 2011). It is mostly found in the form of fibers, which are very strong, insoluble in water, weak acids and bases, and organic solvents. Cellulose molecules adopt an extended and fairly rigid rod-like conformation due to the equatorial conformation of the glucose residues. Multiple hydroxyl groups on glucose from one chain form hydrogen bonds with oxygen atoms on the same or neighboring chain, holding the chains tightly together and forming microfibrils with high tensile strength. This structure classifies cellulose as an important industrial raw material (Shanks, 2013). Regarding cellulose degradation, the

Slika 1. Potrošnja toalet papira i sadržaj celuloze u otpadnoj vodi u nekoliko regiona/zemalja. (preuzeto i modifikovano od Liu i sar., 2022)

Figure 1. Consumption of Toilet Paper and Cellulose Content in Wastewater in Various Regions/Countries (adapted and modified from Liu et al., 2022)

čvrstoće. Ovakva struktura svrstava celulozu pod važnu industrijsku sirovinu (Shanks, 2013). Kada je pak reč o razgradnji celuloze, ključni ali ujedno i limitirajući korak je proces hidrolize sa ekstracelularnom hidrolazom (Munir i sar., 2014). Hidroliza celuloze se sprovodi kroz (ko)saradnju tri različite vrste enzima (Horn i sar., 2012). Prvi korak uključuje endoglukanaze koje nasumično napadaju celulozna vlakna, posebno amorfni deo koji je osetljiviji od kristalnog dela. Zatim, dugačka lančana celuloza hidrolizuje se na molekule kratkog lanca koji dalje prolaze kroz hidrolizu sa egzoglukanazama u drugom koraku. Kao rezultat procesa, molekuli kratkog lanca raspadaju se na molekule šećera sa četiri ili dva ugljenika. U trećoj fazi, β -glukozidaza konačno razgrađuje male molekule do glukoznih monomera. Treba napomenuti da, kako je istaknuto od strane Horn i sar. (2012), postoji više od tri enzima koji direktno ili indirektno učestvuju u hidrolizi celuloze. Na primer, celulozno aktivna hidrolitička polisaharidna monooksigenaza može direktno razložiti kristalni deo celuloze, što može ubrzati razgradnju. Razgradnja celuloze u anaerobnom okruženju ostaje da se razjasni, ali su ograničena istraživanja pokazala da je drugačija od procesa aerobne razgradnje (Wilson, 2011). Ukratko, insolubilnost, visok stepen polimerizacije i stabilnost/čvrstoća povezana sa kristalnom morfologijom dovode do teškoća u vezi sa vezanjem između hidrolaze i celuloze, što rezultuje niskom stopom razgradnje celuloze. Kao što je pomenuto, celuloza čini neophodan deo hemijske potrošnje kiseonika (HPK) i suspendovanih čestica (SS) u influentu komunalnih postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda. Njihova razgradljivost i efikasnost su od visokog interesa u sistemima aktivnog mulja jer utiču na performanse uklanjanja zagađujućih materija. Tabela 1 sumira stopu razgradnje i faktore koji utiču na celulozu u sistemu aktivnog mulja. Polovina ovih studija pokazala je efikasnost razgradnje od oko 80~100%, što nam ukazuje da sistem aktivnog mulja pruža povoljne uslove za efikasnost razgradnje enzimima. Nasuprot tome, niža efikasnost degradacije je takođe primećena u drugim studijama (6,7~13%). Degradacija celuloze u sistemu aktivnog mulja povezana je sa spoljnim ili radnim uslovima, uključujući vreme zadržavanja mulja (SRT), temperaturu i aklimatizaciju. S obzirom da je aktivnost mikroorganizama i enzima osetljiva na temperaturu, Hurwitz i sar. (1961) su istraživanjem pokazali da su aerobne efikasnosti razgradnje celuloze pri temperaturama od 13°C i 23°C bile 6,7% i 87%, što odgovara 11,72 mg/(l·d) i 139,9 mg/(l·d) redom. Pored toga, degradacija celuloze u aktivnom mulju je tesno povezana sa SRT-om. Kada je SRT postavljen na 40 dana, 20 dana i 5 dana (Li i sar., 2019), efikasnosti degradacije celuloze u aerobnim sistemima mulja bile su 83%, 40% i 13%, redom. Li i sar. (2019) su takođe naveli da i bakterije i gljive mogu razgraditi celulozu, ali da razgradnja celuloze u aktivnom mulju može biti dominantnija u slučaju

critical yet limiting step is the hydrolysis process with extracellular hydrolase (Munir et al., 2014). Cellulose hydrolysis is conducted through the cooperation of three different types of enzymes (Horn et al., 2012). The first step involves endoglucanases randomly attacking cellulose fibers, especially the amorphous part, which is more susceptible than the crystalline part. Then, long-chain cellulose is hydrolyzed into short-chain molecules that undergo further hydrolysis by exoglucanases in the second step. As a result, the short-chain molecules break down into four- or two-carbon sugar molecules. In the third phase, β -glucosidase finally breaks down small molecules into glucose monomers. It should be noted that, as highlighted by Horn et al. (2012), there are more than three enzymes that directly or indirectly participate in cellulose hydrolysis. For instance, cellulose-active hydrolytic polysaccharide monooxygenase can directly decompose the crystalline part of cellulose, accelerating degradation. Cellulose degradation in anaerobic environments remains to be clarified, but limited studies showed that it varied from the aerobic degradation process (Wilson, 2011). In summary, insolubility, a high degree of polymerization, and stability/rigidity associated with crystalline morphology create difficulties regarding the binding between hydrolase and cellulose, resulting in a low rate of cellulose degradation. As mentioned, cellulose is an essential component of chemical oxygen demand (COD) and suspended solids (SS) in the influent of municipal wastewater treatment plants. Their degradability and efficiency are of high interest in activated sludge systems as they affect pollutant removal performance. Table 1 summarizes the degradation rate and factors influencing cellulose in the activated sludge system. Half of these studies showed degradation efficiency of about 80~100%, indicating that the activated sludge system provides favorable conditions for enzyme degradation efficiency. Conversely, lower degradation efficiency was also observed in other studies (6,713%). Cellulose degradation in the activated sludge system is closely linked to external or operational conditions, including sludge retention time (SRT), temperature, and acclimatization. Since the activity of microorganisms and enzymes is temperature-sensitive, Hurwitz et al. (1961) showed that the aerobic cellulose degradation efficiencies at temperatures of 13°C and 23°C were 6.7% and 87%, corresponding to 11,72 mg/(L d) and 139,9 mg/(L d), respectively. Moreover, cellulose degradation in activated sludge is closely associated with SRT. When SRT was set at 40 days, 20 days, and 5 days (Li et al., 2019), the aerobic sludge system's cellulose degradation efficiencies were 83%, 40%, and 13%, respectively. Li et al. (2019) also noted that both bacteria and fungi could degrade cellulose, but cellulose degradation in activated sludge might be more dominant in the case of bacteria (*Cellvibrio* species, which can

bakterija (vrsta *Cellvibrio*, koja može brzo proizvesti celulazu). Prema rezultatima u Tabeli 1, oko 30% celuloze može biti degradirano u tipičnom sistemu aktivnog mulja sa SRT-om od 15~20 dana dok će se ostatak akumulirati u višku mulja (Li i sar., 2019). Treba napomenuti da su izvori i kvantitativne metode celuloze korišćene u navedenim eksperimentima dosta varirale i poređenja bi trebalo pažljivo sprovesti.

Na osnovu pregleda literature, maseni tok i transformacija celuloze u tipičnim komunalnim postrojenjima za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda

quickly produce cellulase). According to the results in Table 1, about 30% of cellulose can be degraded in a typical activated sludge system with an SRT of 15~20 days, while the rest will accumulate in the excess sludge (Li et al., 2019). It should be noted that the sources and quantitative methods of cellulose used in the mentioned experiments varied greatly, and comparisons should be conducted carefully.

Based on the literature review, the mass flow and transformation of cellulose in typical municipal wastewater treatment plants (including grit chamber, biological treatment, secondary clarifier, and

Tabela 1. Efikasnosti degradacije celuloze pri aerobnim ili anaerobnim uslovima

Reakcioni uslovi	Reaktor/nivo istraživanja	Vreme (dan)	Temperatura (°C)	Koncentracija celuloze (mg/l)	Nivo degradacije (mg/l-dan)	Efikasnost degradacije (%)*
Aerobni [1]	Process sa aktivnim muljem/velika skala	3	12-13 23	524,73 482,97	11,72 139,9	6,7 87
Aerobni [2]	SBR/ laboratorijska	5 20 40	22	200	26,6 76,8 164,6	13 40 83
Aerobni [3]	Process sa aktivnim muljem/velika skala	4,8	/	98,99	16,85	80
Aerobni [4]	-/laboratorijska	18	58	/	/	80
Aerobni [5]	SBR/ laboratorijska	1/4	22-24	42	144,48	86
Aerobni [6]	SBR/ laboratorijska	1/3	10 33	35,5	85,52 95,64	80,3 89,8
Aerobni [7]	SBR/ laboratorijska	5/24	/	149,5	372	51,8
Anoksični [7]	SBR/ laboratorijska	1/24	/	155	132	3,5
Anaerobni [8]	Digestija/ laboratorijska	15	35 55	/ /	/ /	57 62
Anaerobni [9]	Digestija/ pilot	20 20	17 24	/ /	/ /	50 100

*Efikasnost degradacije se odnosi na procenat mineralizacije celuloze mikroorganizmima, dok je celuloza određena na osnovu glukoze ili pomoću Schweitzer metode.

[1] Hurwitz i sar. (1961)

[2] Li i sar. (2019).

[3] Reijken i sar. (2018).

[4] Rossetti i sar. (2021).

[5] Ahmed i sar. (2019).

[6] Kim i sar. (2022).

[7] Ahmed (2020).

[8] Ghasimi i sar. (2016).

[9] Ruiken i sar. (2013).

Table 1. The efficiency of cellulose degradation under aerobic or anaerobic conditions

Condition	Reactor/Scale	Time (days)	Temp. (°C)	C. cellulose (mg/L)	Degradation rate (mg/L·d)	Degradation efficiency (%)*
Aerobic ^[1]	Activated sludge process/ full-scale	3	12-13 23	524.73 482.97	11.72 139.9	6.7 87
Aerobic ^[2]	SBR/ lab-scale	5 20 40	22	200	26.6 76.8 164.6	13 40 83
Aerobic ^[3]	Activated sludge/ full-scale process	4.8	/	98.99	16.85	80
Aerobic ^[4]	-/lab-scale	18	58	/	/	80
Aerobic ^[5]	SBR/ lab-scale	1/4	22-24	42	144.48	86
Aerobic ^[6]	SBR/ lab-scale	1/3	10 33	35.5	85.52 95.64	80.3 89.8
Aerobic ^[7]	SBR/ lab-scale	5/24	/	149.5	372	51.8
Anoxic ^[7]	SBR/ lab-scale	1/24	/	155	132	3.5
Anaerobic ^[8]	Digester/lab-scale	15	35 55	/ /	/ /	57 62
Anaerobic ^[9]	Digester/pilot-scale	20 20	17 24	/ /	/ /	50 100

* Degradation efficiency refers to the percentage of cellulose mineralization by microorganisms and cellulose was determined based on glucose or Schweitzer method.

[1] Hurwitz i sar. (1961)

[2] Li i sar. (2019).

[3] Reijken i sar. (2018).

[4] Rossetti i sar. (2021).

[5] Ahmed i sar. (2019).

[6] Kim i sar. (2022).

[7] Ahmed (2020).

[8] Ghasimi i sar. (2016).

[9] Ruiken i sar. (2013).

(uključujući peskolov, biološki tretman, sekundarni taložnik i anaerobni tank za digestiju mulja) sa i bez primarnog taložnika su prikazani na slici 2. Kao što je prikazano, nakon što celuloza uđe u postrojenje za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda, primarni tretman ima značajan uticaj na celulozu. Peskolov može zadržati oko 20% celuloze dok posebno dizajnirani primarni taložnik za uklanjanje čvrstih čestica može postići uklanjanje od čak 80% (na osnovu količine koja ulazi u primarni taložnik) (Li i sar., 2020; Ruiken i sar., 2013). Dok ako posmatramo liniju mulja veći deo celuloznih vlakana se degradira u anaerobnoj digestiji 38%, dok 30% zaostaje u muljnoj pogači koja se dalje najčešće primenjuje u poljoprivredne svrhe. Kao što je već navedeno, celuloza je nerastvorljiva i bogata funkcionalnim grupama koje čine celulozu lako vezanom za druge čestice u otpadnim vodama (Rana i sar., 2021). Stoga, fizičke metode separacije mogu efikasno odvojiti celulozu iz otpadnih voda, što takođe inspiriše tehničko rešenje za efikasnu rekuperaciju celuloze o čemu će biti reči u nastavku. Kao što je

anaerobic sludge digestion tank) with and without a primary clarifier are depicted in Figure 2. As shown, after cellulose enters the wastewater treatment plant, the primary treatment significantly affects cellulose. The grit chamber can retain about 20% of cellulose, while a specifically designed primary clarifier for solid particle removal can achieve removal of up to 80% (based on the amount entering the primary clarifier) (Li et al., 2020; Ruiken et al., 2013). Meanwhile, in the sludge line, a large portion of cellulose fibers degrades during anaerobic digestion (38%), while 30% remains in the sludge cake, which is often applied for agricultural purposes. As previously mentioned, cellulose is insoluble and rich in functional groups, making it readily bound to other particles in wastewater (Rana et al., 2021). Therefore, physical separation methods can effectively separate cellulose from wastewater, which also inspires technical solutions for efficient cellulose recovery, as discussed below. As it is shown in Figure 2, the primary clarifier affects the amount of cellulose entering the biological

prikazano na slici 2, primarni taložnik utiče na količinu celuloze koja ulazi u biološki rezervoar, time utičući na količinu razgradnje. Ukoliko posmatramo deo na slici 2 proces bez primarnog taložnika, oko 66% ulazne celuloze može biti razgrađeno i uklonjeno u biološkom rezervoaru dok samo 10% ulazne celuloze prolazi kroz biološku razgradnju sa taložnikom. Što se tiče troškova rada postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda, celuloza može izazvati dodatne troškove rada bez obzira na situaciju, povećavajući višak mulja (sa primarnim taložnikom) ili intenzivirajući aeraciju (bez primarnog taložnika), što ima praktičan značaj i podsticaj za primenu rekuperacije celuloze (Liu i sar., 2022). Nakon biološkog rezervoara, deo celuloze će biti zadržan u sekundarnom taložniku dok će mali deo oticati u prijemno vodno telo sa otpadnom vodom. Treba napomenuti da prisustvo primarnog taložnika ima očigledan pozitivan efekat na smanjenje sadržaja celuloze i SS-a u otpadnoj vodi. Analitičke metode za određivanje sadržaja (koncentracije) celuloze u otpadnim vodama i mulju sa postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda se uglavnom zasnivaju na kiseloj i enzimskoj hidrolizi, kao i na gravimetrijskoj metodi sa Švajcerovim (Schweitzer) reagensom. Švajcerova metoda se pak u dosadašnjoj literaturi pokazala kao veoma pouzdana i najčešće korišćena metoda, što je ujedno služilo i za efikasnost rekuperacije celuloznih vlakana sa postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda (Bečelić-Tomin i Kerkez, 2022).

reservoir, thereby influencing the degradation amount. In the part of Figure 2 representing the process without a primary clarifier, approximately 66% of the input cellulose can be degraded and removed in the biological reservoir, while only 10% of the input cellulose undergoes biological degradation with the clarifier. Regarding the operational costs of wastewater treatment plants, cellulose can incur additional operating costs regardless of the situation, either by increasing excess sludge (with a primary clarifier) or intensifying aeration (without a primary clarifier), which has practical significance and incentives for cellulose recovery implementation (Liu et al., 2022). After the biological reservoir, a portion of cellulose will be retained by the secondary clarifier, while a small portion will be discharged into the receiving water body with the wastewater. It should be noted that the presence of a primary clarifier has an apparent positive effect on reducing the cellulose and SS content in wastewater. Analytical methods for determining the cellulose content (concentration) in wastewater and sludge from wastewater treatment plants are mainly based on acidic and enzymatic hydrolysis, as well as gravimetric methods with Schweitzer reagent. The Schweitzer method proved to be very reliable. It is commonly used in the literature, serving as the basis for the efficiency of cellulose fiber recovery from wastewater treatment plants (Bečelić-Tomin & Kerkez, 2022).

Slika 2. Sudbina i transformacija celuloze duž linije tretmana otpadnih voda (a) sa primarnim taložnikom i (b) bez primarnog taložnika (preuzeto i modifikovano od Bečelić-Tomin i Kerkez., 2022)

Figure 2. The fate and transformation of cellulose along the wastewater treatment line (a) with a primary clarifier and (b) without a primary clarifier (adapted and modified from Bečelić-Tomin and Kerkez, 2022).

3. REKUPERACIJA I VALORIZACIJA CELULOZE IZ OTPADNIH VODA

3.1 Hronologija rekuperacije celuloze iz otpadnih voda sa PPOV

Interes i prepoznavanje celuloze u otpadnim vodama može se pratiti od negde kraja 1960-ih. Hurwitz i sar. (1961) primetili su neobičnost da se mulj promenio iz granularnog u vlaknast, što je kasnije razjašnjeno kao posledica prisustva celuloze i sproveli su preliminarna istraživanja o njenoj razgradnji, te pretpostavili da temperatura utiče na sadržaj celuloze u mulju. Godine 2002., Honda i sar. (2002) su predložili ideju o izdvajanju celuloze iz otpadnog mulja kako bi se koristila kao biomasa, prepoznajući da primarni mulj sadrži značajnu količinu celuloze (oko 20%, u pogledu SS). Zatim su predložili primenu visokotemperaturne razblažene kiseline kao jednostavan metod za sprovođenje rekuperacije celuloze. Prema masenom toku celuloze u procesu prečišćavanja otpadnih voda (slika 2), tipičan primarni taložnik može efikasno zadržati 68% celuloze u ulaznoj vodi i kondenzovati je u mulju. Dakle, primarni mulj može poslužiti kao prekursor za proizvodnju celuloze. Najvažnije je da se rekuperacija celuloze treba sprovoditi pre bioloških jedinica gde celuloza podleže značajnoj degradaciji. Drugim rečima, najbolje mesto za „presretanje“ celuloze čini se da je u primarnom tretmanu, pre biološkog ili putem inovativnog procesa. Nakon toga, postoji nekoliko sporadičnih

3. RECOVERY AND VALORIZATION OF CELLULOSE FROM WASTEWATER

3.1 Chronology of Cellulose Recovery from Wastewater in WWTPs

Interest in and recognition of cellulose in wastewater can be traced back to the late 1960s. Hurwitz et al. (1961) observed the unusual change of sludge from granular to fibrous, later clarified as a result of cellulose presence. They conducted preliminary research on its degradation and speculated that temperature affects the cellulose content in the sludge. In 2002, Honda et al. (2002) proposed the idea of extracting cellulose from sewage sludge for use as biomass, recognizing that primary sludge contains a significant amount of cellulose (about 20%, in terms of SS). They then proposed the application of high-temperature diluted acid as a simple method for cellulose recovery. According to the mass flow of cellulose in the wastewater treatment process (Figure 2), a typical primary clarifier can effectively retain 68% of cellulose in the influent and concentrate it in the sludge. Thus, primary sludge can serve as a precursor for cellulose production. It is crucial that cellulose recovery has to be conducted prior to biological units where cellulose undergoes significant degradation. In other words, the best interception point for cellulose seems to be in the primary treatment before biological or through an innovative process. Afterwards, there were several

pokušaja rekuperacije celuloze, ali to nije postalo glavno interesovanje i fokus među tehnologijama za rekuperaciju resursa. Sa transformacijom uloge otpadnih voda iz nosioca otpada u nosioca resursa, resursi koji se mogu reciklirati iz otpadnih voda su u potpunosti istraženi. Studija Ruiken i sar. (2013) ponovo je privukla pažnju na rekuperaciju celuloze iz otpadnih voda uvodeći inovativni proces rotacione trakaste/ramske filter prese (RBF) kako bi zamenili primarni taložnik (Cipolletta i sar., 2019). Zaista, RBF je do sada najperspektivnija, a jednostavna tehnologija za rekuperaciju celuloze, o čemu će biti detaljno dalje diskutovano. Nedavno je takođe predložen i testiran metod sa jonskim tečnostima za izdvajanje celuloze iz mulja (Glinska i sar., 2019), što je sumirano u tabeli 2 zajedno sa pomenute dve tehnologije.

sporadic attempts at cellulose recovery, but it did not become a major interest and focus among resource recovery technologies. With the transformation of the role of wastewater from a waste carrier to a resource carrier, recyclable resources from wastewater were fully explored. Ruiken et al. (2013) study re-attracted attention to cellulose recovery from wastewater by introducing the innovative Rotating Belt Filter Press (RBFP) process to replace the primary clarifier (Cipolletta et al., 2019). Indeed, RBFP is so far the most promising and simple technology for cellulose recovery, which will be further discussed in detail. Recently, a method with ionic liquids for cellulose extraction from sludge was also proposed and tested (Glinska et al., 2019), summarized in Table 2 along with the two mentioned technologies.

Tabela 2. Tehnologije rekuperacije celuloze

Tehnologija rekuperacije	Procedura	Performanse rekuperacije	Referenca
Hidroliza pri visokoj temperaturi sa razblaženom kiselinom	Tretirano sa 0,3% sumporne kiseline pri 130°C, laboratorijska skala, primarni mulj	Celuloza je kondenzovana od 20% do 69% ili više (u odnosu na početni sadržaj celuloze u primarnom mulju)	Honda i sar. (2002)
Jonske tečnosti	Pred-alkalno + post-kiselinsko tretiranje, laboratorijska skala, Nerada granulirani mulj	10~11 g celuloze/kg mulja (suva materija)	Espíndola i sar. (2021)
	Jonska tečnost: mulj = 5:1 (g/mL), temperatura 100°C, laboratorijska skala, industrijski osušeni papirni mulj	Procenat celuloze je povećan sa 24% na 56% (u suvoj materiji); zaostaju protein i pepeo nakon procesa	Glinska i sar. (2019)
	Jonska tečnost: mulj = 7~17:1 (g/ml), temperatura 35-60°C, laboratorijska skala, primarni mulj	Čistoća celuloze od 26% (ostaci uključuju lignin, proteine i pepeo)	Glinska i sar. (2020)
Rotirajuća ramska filter presa (RBF)	350 µm, velika skala, otpadne vode	76 mg-celuloze/l otpadnih voda čini 32% influentnih suspendovanih čestica	Ruiken i sar. (2013)
	350 µm, velika skala, otpadne vode	59 mg-celuloze/l otpadnih voda ili 79% celuloze u influentu	Ahmed i sar. (2019)
	350 µm, velika skala, otpadne vode	162 g-SS/kg ili 105 g-celuloze/kg-filtriranog mulja	Espíndola i sar. (2021)
	350 µm/210 µm, velika skala, otpadne vode	35 mg-celuloze/l otpadnih voda, bez značajne razlike sa 210 µm	Da Ros i sar. (2020)

Table 2. Cellulose recovery technologies.

Recovery method	Processing procedure	Recovery performance	Reference
Hydrolysis at high temperature with dilute acid	Treated by 0.3% sulfuric acid under 130 °C, lab-scale, primary sludge	Cellulose is condensed from 20% to 69% or more (relative to the initial cellulose content of the primary sludge)	Honda et al. (2002)
Ionic liquid	Pre-alkaline + postacid treatment, in lab-scale, granular sludge	10~11 g cellulose/kg sludge (dry matter)	Espíndola et al. (2021)
	Ionic liquid: sludge = 5:1 (g/mL), temperature 100 °C, lab-scale, industrial dried paper sludge	The percentage of cellulose increased from 24% to 56% (in dry matter); protein and ash remain after the process	Glinska et al. (2019)
	Ionic liquid: sludge = 7~17:1 (g/mL), temperature 35~60 °C, lab-scale, primary sludge	Cellulose purity of 26% (other residual includes lignin, proteins, and ashes)	Glinska et al. (2020)
Rotating Belt Filter (RBF)	350 µm, full-scale, wastewater	76 mg-cellulose/Lwastewater Accounted for 32% of the influent SS	Ruiken et al. (2013)
	350 µm, full-scale, wastewater	59 mg-cellulose/Lwastewater or 79% cellulose in influent	Ahmed et al. (2019)
	350 µm, full-scale, wastewater	162 g-SS/kg or 105 g cellulose/kg-filter sludge	Espíndola et al. (2021)
	350 µm/210 µm, full-scale, wastewater	35 mg-cellulose/Lwastewater, no significant difference with 210 µm	Da Ros et al. (2020)

3.2. Tehnologije rekuperacije

Tehnologije rekuperacije celuloze sa postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda podrazumevaju mehanički postupak (primarni tretman/taložnik), odnosno primenu tehnologije mikroprosejavanja (sita sa promerom <0,5 mm), zatim primenu rotirajuće filter prese i na kraju primenu jonskih tečnosti, zahvaljujući visokom afinitetu jonskih tečnosti ka rastvaranju/razgradnji celuloznih vlakana. Zahvaljujući već pomenutim funkcionalnim grupama celuloze i nerastvorljivosti u vodi, celulozna vlakna lako stupaju u interakciju sa drugim česticama prisutnim u otpadnoj vodi koja dolazi na postrojenje za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda. Ova sposobnost i svojstva celuloznih vlakana doprinose samim tim i mogućnosti izdvajanja (rekuperacije) u primarnom taložniku/tretmanu. Tehnologije mikroprosejavanja mogu biti još brži i efikasniji put izdvajanja celuloze, usled primene sistema rešetaka a zatim grubih i finih sita (<0,5 mm) na početku postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda pre primarnog taložnika, za zadržavanje celuloznih vlakana na membrani sita (Li i sar., 2019, Liu i sar.,

3.2. Recovery technologies

Recovery technologies from wastewater treatment plants involve mechanical processes (primary treatment/clarifiers), such as micro sieving technology (screens with a diameter <0.5 mm), followed by the use of rotating belt filter presses and, finally, the application of ionic liquids, thanks to their high affinity towards dissolving/degrading cellulose fibers. Due to the functional groups present in cellulose and its insolubility in water, cellulose fibers readily interact with other particles present in wastewater entering the treatment plant. This capability and properties of cellulose fibers contribute to the possibility of their separation (recovery) in primary clarifiers/treatment. Micro sieving technologies can offer even faster and more efficient means of cellulose separation, achieved through the use of bar screens followed by coarse and fine screens (<0.5 mm) at the beginning of the wastewater treatment plant, before the primary clarifiers, to retain cellulose fibers on the screen membrane (Li et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2022). The significant advantage of pre-filtration at wastewater

2022). Značajna prednost predfiltracije na postrojenju za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda je smanjenje troškova i potrošnje energije za aerobni digestor, dok primena sita sa ovako sitnim porama nije baš prihvaćena na industrijskoj skali usled skuplje izrade sita, mogućnosti začepeljavanja i zagušenja na postrojenju. Honda i sar. su još 2002. godine rekuperisali celulozu iz primarnog mulja primenom metode visokotemperaturne hidrolize razblaženom sumpornom kiselinom (tabela 2). Rekuperisani mulj je tretiran razblaženim rastvorom sumporne kiseline na temperaturi od 130°C tokom 60 minuta. Rezidual nakon tretmana je neutralizovan pranjem i sušenjem pri niskim temperaturama, pri čemu se na ovaj način dobila celuloza sa malim udelom nečistoća. Čistoća celuloze zavisi od procentualnog udela celulozih vlakana prisutnih u primarnom mulju kao i koncentracije rastvora primenjene kiseline. Generalno, ispitivanja su pokazala da sadržaj celuloze preko 20% u primarnom mulju ovom metodom može rekuperisati celulozu (dobiti proizvod) sa 70% čistoće. Međutim, ova metoda rekuperacije trenutno još uvek ostaje pri laboratorijskoj skali primene. Dalji korak rekuperacije celulozih vlakana na osnovu filtracije jeste primena rotacione trakaste/ramske filter prese sa ispunom (RBF). U poređenju sa prethodne dve tehnologije, RBF može pružiti rešenje koje je jednostavnije i ekonomičnije za izdvajanje celuloze iz otpadnih voda (Ruiken i sar., 2013). RBF je kompaktna uređaj koji se sastoji od tri modula, uključujući filter ploču određenih veličina pora membrane, uređaj za čišćenje i prihvatni rezervoar za sitne čestice (Screencap, 2017). U nekim zemljama, RBF-ovi se takođe koriste za kontrolu preliivanja kombinovane kanalizacije. Što se tiče njihovih performansi, veličina pora filter ploče pretežno određuje efikasnost uklanjanja SS-a, dok uređaj za čišćenje utiče na pouzdanost kontinuiranog rada. Generalno, manja veličina pora membrane na situ filter ploče obično može osigurati veće uklanjanje SS-a (tabela 2). Istraživanja su pokazala da filter presa sa veličinom pora membrane od 350µm je najefikasnija za primenu jer zadržava 30-60% mulja (muljna pogača) pri čemu utiče na efikasnije prečišćavanje otpadne vode smanjujući koncentraciju hemijske potrošnje kiseonika (HPK) za 10-30% (Peeters i sar., 2014; Ruiken i sar., 2013). Osim toga, kako je pokazano u istraživanjima Da Ros i sar. (2020), i brzina opterećenja čvrstim materijama ima značajan uticaj na uklanjanje SS-a. Što se tiče veličine pora od 350 µm, efikasnost uklanjanja SS-a povećala se sa 50% na 78% povećanjem brzine opterećenja SS-a sa 35 na 58 kg TSS/(m²·h). Veća količina opterećenja čvrstim materijama doprinosi formiranju matičnog sloja filtera ili kolača koji će značajno povećati zadržavanje SS-a, čak i manje od veličine pora membrane. Kada se formira kolač, efikasnost zadržavanja SS-a skoro je nezavisna od veličine pora, ali zavisi od hidrauličnog protoka (Rusten i Lundar, 2006). Međutim, debljina kolača može dovesti do preliivanja i neuspešnosti procesa. Stoga je efikasan modul za čišćenje takođe

treatment plants is the reduction in costs and energy consumption for aerobic digestion, although the use of screens with such small pores is not widely accepted on an industrial scale due to the higher cost of screen fabrication and the potential for clogging and fouling at the plant. As early as 2002, Honda et al. recovered cellulose from primary sludge using a high-temperature hydrolysis method with dilute sulfuric acid (Table 2). The recovered sludge was treated with a dilute sulfuric acid solution at 130°C for 60 minutes. The residual material after treatment was neutralized by washing and drying at low temperatures, resulting in cellulose with low impurity content. The purity of cellulose depends on the percentage of cellulose fibers present in the primary sludge and on the concentration of the used acid solution. Generally, studies showed that this method could recover cellulose (yielding a product) with 70% purity from primary sludge containing over 20% cellulose fibers. However, this recovery method currently remains at the laboratory scale. The next step in cellulose recovery following filtration is the use of rotating belt/plate and frame filter presses (RBF). Compared to the previous two technologies, RBF offers a relatively simpler and more economical solution for cellulose separation from wastewater (Ruiken et al., 2013). RBF is a compact device consisting of three modules, including a filter plate with specific membrane pore sizes, a cleaning device, and a collection tank for fine particles (Screencap, 2017). In some countries, RBFs are also used for combined sewer overflow control. Regarding their performance, the pore size of the filter plate largely determines the efficiency of SS removal, while the cleaning device affects the reliability of continuous operation. Generally, a smaller membrane pore size on the filter plate can ensure higher SS removal rates (Table 2). Research showed that a filter press with a membrane pore size of 350 µm is the most effective, retaining 30-60% of sludge (sludge cake), thereby contributing to more efficient wastewater treatment by reducing the concentration of chemical oxygen demand (COD) by 10-30% (Peeters et al., 2014; Ruiken et al., 2013). Furthermore, as it was demonstrated in studies by Da Ros et al. (2020), the rate of solid matter loading also had a significant impact on SS removal. Regarding a pore size of 350 µm, the SS removal efficiency increased from 50% to 78% with an increase in the solid matter loading rate from 35 to 58 kg TSS/(m²·h). A higher loading of solid matter contributes to the formation of a filter cake, which significantly increases SS retention, even below the membrane pore size. Once a cake is formed, the SS retention efficiency is almost independent of the pore size but depends on the hydraulic flow rate. However, the thickness of the cake may lead to overflowing and process failure. Therefore, an efficient cleaning module is also necessary and should be carefully designed (e.g., knives, high-pressure water spraying, air flushing, and/or hot water washing). It generally showed

neophodan i trebao bi biti pažljivo dizajniran (npr. nož, prskanje visokim pritiskom vode, ispiranje vazduhom i/ili pranje toplom vodom). Generalno je pokazano da prisustvo celuloznih vlakana veličine 1mm u otpadnoj vodi koja dolazi na postrojenje za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda i primena rotirajuće filter prese sa ispunom je u mogućnosti da zadrži do 40% mulja koji sadrži celulozu. Pomenute filter prese se mogu instalirati na početku postrojenja umesto primarnog taložnika ili nakon peskolova, pri čemu je rekuperacija celuloze najveća, ili je pak moguće instalirati prese i na izlaznoj cevi nakon sekundarnog taložnika pri čemu na taj način ukupna količina rekuperisane celuloze je znatno manja. Trenutno je oko 700 ovakvih filter presa instalirano/primenjeno na velikoj skali širom Evrope i Amerike. Na primer u Holandiji (Geestmerambacht postrojenje za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda), rotacione filter prese se primenjuju nakon peskolova na postrojenju za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda, pri čemu rekuperišu oko 400 kg celuloze svakog dana, koja se zatim prodaje pod Recell® brendom i koristi za razne potrebe kupaca (Liu i sar., 2022). Kao takva, tehnologija više nije ograničenje koje bi sprečavalo primenu rekuperacije celuloze. Primena jonskih tečnosti podrazumeva rekuperaciju celuloze iz muljne pogače (čvrst materijal, suv mulj), tretiranjem i potapanjem muljnog kolača u jonsku tečnost, praćenu precipitacijom ugljenih hidrata (celuloze) dejstvom metanola. Nakon centrifugiranja i termalnog sušenja, rekuperisana celuloza se kondenzuje i prečišćava. Na ovaj način se ipak ne mogu u potpunosti ukloniti proteini i zaostali pepeo iz dobijenog proizvoda, stoga ova metoda zahteva dalju optimizaciju procesa, a svakako zahteva i visoke energetske troškove kao i dodatak hemikalija čime limitira svoju primenu na velikoj industrijskoj skali.

3.3. Valorizacija rekuperisane celuloze sa PPOV

Potencijalna primena rekuperisane celuloze je raznolika i može se podeliti u dve kategorije: za interne potrebe na samom postrojenju za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda, ili kao tržišni proizvod. Prva kategorija podrazumeva primenu kao goriva/biomase za postrojenje za proizvodnju biogasa (Wouters i Euverink, 2017), zatim kao flokulant (Grenda i sar., 2020; Zhang i sar., 2020), za smanjenje troškova i upotrebe kiseonika u aerobnom digestoru (Radini i sar., 2021), smanjenje zagađivanja/začepljenja pora membrane kada se koriste membranski reaktori za dalje prečišćavanje, bolje performanse dobijene muljne pogače. Dok druga kategorija podrazumeva primenu rekuperisane celuloze kao sirovog materijala - sirovine za industriju papira, dobijanje bioplastike, kao građevinski materijal (kao zamena određenog udela u asfaltu, malteru, pri čemu poboljšava čvrstoću materijala i smanjuje koeficijent otpora pari), sirovina za industriju fermentacije, sirovina za proizvodnju nanoceluloze (adsorbent, dodatak plastici, papiru i kartonu), sirovina za izdvajanje

that the presence of cellulose fibers sized 1 mm in wastewater entering the treatment plant and the application of rotating belt filter presses with packing could retain up to 40% of sludge containing cellulose. These filter presses can be installed at the beginning of the plant instead of primary clarifiers or after grit chambers, where cellulose recovery is the highest, or they can be installed on the outlet pipe after secondary clarifiers, resulting in a significantly lower total amount of recovered cellulose. Currently, around 700 such filter presses are installed/applied on a large scale across Europe and America. For instance, in the Netherlands (at the Geestmerambacht wastewater treatment plant), rotating belt filter presses are applied after grit chambers, recovering around 400 kg of cellulose daily, which is then sold under the Recell® brand and used for various customer needs (Liu et al., 2022). As such, the technology is no longer a limitation preventing the application of cellulose recovery. The application of ionic liquids involves cellulose recovery from sludge cake (solid material, dry sludge) by treating and immersing the sludge cake in ionic liquid, followed by the precipitation of carbohydrates (cellulose) with methanol. After centrifugation and thermal drying, the recovered cellulose is condensed and purified. However, this method cannot completely remove proteins and residual ash from the resulting product. Therefore, this method requires further process optimization and undoubtedly involves high energy costs and the addition of chemicals, limiting its application on a large industrial scale.

3.3. Valorization of recovered cellulose from WWTPs

The potential application of recovered cellulose is diverse and can be divided into two categories: for internal needs at the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) or as a marketable product. The first category involves its use as fuel/biomass for biogas production at the plant (Wouters & Euverink, 2017), as a flocculant (Grenda et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020) to reduce oxygen consumption and costs in aerobic digesters (Radini et al., 2021), to reduce fouling of membrane pores when using membrane reactors for further purification, and to improve the performance of dewatered sludge. The second category involves the application of recovered cellulose as a raw material for various purposes - raw material for the paper industry, bioplastics, construction materials (as a replacement for a certain proportion in asphalt, mortar, improving material strength and reducing steam resistance coefficient), raw material for fermentation industry, raw material for nanocellulose production (as an adsorbent, additive to plastic, paper, and cardboard), raw material for volatile fatty acid extraction, raw material for fertilizers, etc. For example, recovered cellulose is used in the construction industry as a component for strengthening adhesives and in

isparljivih masnih kiselina, sirovina za đubrivo itd. Na primer, rekuperisana celuloza se koristi u građevinskoj industriji kao komponenta za ojačavanje lepкова i u industriji papira kao sirovina (Palmieri i sar., 2019; Li i sar., 2020). Papirni proizvodi (uključujući toalet papir) proizvedeni od obnovljene celuloze ispunjavaju standarde bezbednosti i higijene, ali problem "faktora odbojnosti" treba uzeti u obzir. Pored toga, predložen je i isproban još jedan put za unapređenje rekuperacije celuloze u proizvod visoke dodatne vrednosti, tj. nanocelulozu (Espíndola i sar., 2021). Ispitivanje je pokazalo da je ekonomičnije proizvoditi nanocelulozu iz otpadnih voda u poređenju sa proizvodnjom iz drvene pulpe i poljoprivrednog otpada. Osim toga, generisana nanoceluloza odgovara trenutnim komercijalnim standardima u pogledu odnosa morfologije i hemijske strukture. Koji krajnji proizvod treba usvojiti zavisi od potražnje na tržištu, primenjenih troškova i održivosti date tehnologije. Važno je napomenuti da ne postoji univerzalan put za valorizaciju rekuperisane celuloze, te da je potrebno sprovesti sveobuhvatnu ekonomsku i ekološku analizu kako bi se utvrdilo koji proizvod ima najveći potencijal za ponovnu upotrebu.

4. ZAKLJUČAK

Rekuperacija resursa iz otpadnih voda u proizvode sa dodatom vrednošću može značajno doprineti prihodima postrojenja za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda, što predstavlja primarni i direktni podsticaj za praksu rekuperacije otpadnih voda. Kao jedan od potencijalnih resursa u otpadnim vodama sa PPOV, rekuperacija celuloze bi trebalo biti temeljno istražena i valorizovana kako bi se uskladila sa ciljevima cirkularne ekonomije. Na osnovu svega pomenutog, možemo zaključiti sledeće:

1. Sadržaj celuloze u otpadnim vodama varira, ali i pored toga, pojedina razvijena područja, kao i određene zemlje u razvoju, imaju potencijal za praktičnu primenu rekuperacije celuloze.
2. Degradacija celuloze u aktivnom mulju je značajna, a posebno ukoliko tehnologija ne uključuje primenu primarnog taložnika.
3. Predložene tehnologije za rekuperaciju celuloze iz mulja i otpadnih voda sa PPOV su: visokotemperaturna hidroliza sa razblaženim kiselinama, primena jonskih tečnosti, kao i primena rotacione trakaste/ramske filter prese sa ispunom (RBF). Posebno se izdvaja kao efikasna i preporučuje primena RBF nakon peskolova.
4. Rekuperacija celuloze može smanjiti troškove aeracije, količinu otpadnog mulja i/ili potrošnju hemikalija. Dobijeni rekuperisani proizvodi mogu biti plasirani na tržište ili ponovno korišćeni interno u postrojenjima za prečišćavanje otpadnih voda.

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the paper industry as a raw material (Palmieri et al., 2019; Li et al., 2020). Paper products (including toilet paper) made from recycled cellulose meet safety and hygiene standards, but the "repellency factor" issue should be considered. Furthermore, another experimental approach was proposed to enhance cellulose recovery into a high-value-added product, i.e., nanocellulose (Espíndola et al., 2021). The study showed that it is more economical to produce nanocellulose from wastewater compared to production from wood pulp and agricultural waste. Additionally, the generated nanocellulose meets current commercial standards in terms of morphology and chemical structure ratio. The choice of the final product to adopt depends on market demand, applied costs, and the sustainability of the given technology. It is important to note that there is no universal path for valorizing recovered cellulose, and a comprehensive economic and environmental analysis is required to determine which product has the greatest potential for reuse.

4. CONCLUSION

Resource recovery from wastewater into value-added products can bring significant additional revenue to wastewater treatment plants, which is always a primary and direct incentive for wastewater valorization practices. As one of the resources in wastewater, cellulose recovery should be fully explored and valorized to align with the goals of the circular economy. Based on all the mentioned points, we can conclude that:

- i) The content of cellulose in wastewater varies, but some developed areas, as well as some developing countries, have the potential for practical implementation of cellulose recovery.
- ii) Cellulose degradation in activated sludge is significant, and particularly without a primary clarifier, most incoming cellulose can be mineralized aerobically.
- iii) High-temperature dilute acid hydrolysis, ionic liquids, and RBF are proposed technologies for cellulose recovery from sludge or wastewater. Specifically, the application of RBF after grit removal is highly recommended.
- iv) Cellulose recovery can reduce aeration costs, the amount of waste sludge, and/or chemical consumption. The resulting recovered products can be marketed or reused internally at WWTPs.

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